

On Some Fluorophenazines

K. D. BANERJI, A. K. D. MAZUMDAR, K. KUMAR and S. K. GUHA

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812007

Manuscript received 8 July 1978, accepted 20 November 1978

Several indophenazines, phenanthraphenazines and acenaphthaphenazines have been described, all of which contain a fluorine atom in the benzene moiety.

THE indophenazine group of dyes, have been studied from different points of view. Thus Buu-Hoi *et al*¹⁻⁶ have investigated their carcinogenic effect, their action on tuberculosis bacilli, etc., while Friedmann⁶ has patented a few indophenazines as optical bleaches. Again Guzral *et al*⁷ have observed good antispasmodic activity of some indophenazines while still others have studied them as dyes⁸⁻¹².

Similarly, phenanthraphenazines have been studied not only as dyes¹³ but their anti-tumor and carcinogenic activity have also been reported^{14,15}. Acenaphthaphenazines have primarily been studied as dye-stuffs^{11,16-19}. Again several fluorinated compounds have been found to possess significant physiological properties including anti-tumor activity²⁰⁻²⁴.

Phenazines carrying fluorine atoms have not been reported so far and in the present communication we describe the preparation and properties of the new phenazines of the type (I, II & III), all of which contain a fluorine atom in the benzene moiety at position 2 or 3.

For the purpose of the present work, 4-fluoro-*o*-phenylenediamine has been condensed with

(a) isatin and its 5-bromo-, 5-chloro-, 5-iodo-, 5-nitro-, 5-bromo-7-nitro- and 5:7-dibromo-derivatives to give compounds of type I,

(b) phenanthraquinone and its 2-nitro- and 2:7-dinitro-derivatives to produce phenazines of type II,

(c) acenaphthaquinone and its 3-bromo-, 3-chloro- and 3:4-dinitro derivatives, to yield the dyes of type III.

Details about these dyes are given in the Table. In a few cases condensation may lead to the generation of two possible structural isomers. It was, however, found that one isomer was predominantly produced which could be obtained in a pure state. The colours of the indophenazines range between yellow, brown and deep orange although one of them (Sl. No. 3 of Table) is faintly green. The acenaphthaphenazines have buffviolet colour. All the phenazine dyes were generally very little soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, etc., but were soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. They analysed correctly for nitrogen.

Shades of dyes obtained from the diketones listed above and 4-methoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine are available in literature^{12,18,19} and a comparison of the shades of the corresponding dyes presently obtained reveal that a fluorine atom is capable of producing a somewhat enhanced bathochromic effect. Biological activity of a few of the above dyes is proposed to be undertaken.

Experimental

The following general procedure was adopted:

To a clear solution of the diketone in a minimum volume of hot acetic acid was added an equimolar proportion of the *o*-phenylenediamine. The products separated immediately in most cases but to ensure complete reaction, the mixture was gently

TABLE

Sl. No.	Reactants	Name	Appearance ; solvent.	M.P.°C ; yield crude	Mol. formula	Analysis Required	Analysis Result Found
1.	I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro IP	Brown Pyridine	291-99 63%	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ F	N=17.7	N=18.28
2.	5-Bromo I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-9-Bromo IP	Deep yellow Pyridine	325-26 73%	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ BrF	N=13.29	N=13.6
3.	5-Iodo I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-9-Iodo IP	Faint green Pyridine	358-60 34%	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ FI	N=11.57	N=12.46
4.	5-Nitro I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-9-nitro IP	Brown Pyridine	319-20 100%	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₄ FO ₂	N=19.85	N=20.12
5.	5 : 7-Dibromo I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-7 : 9-dibromo IP	Deep Brown Pyridine	295-96 98%	C ₁₄ H ₉ Br ₂ FN ₃	N=10.63	N=11.25
6.	5-Bromo-7-nitro I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-7-Bromo-9-nitro IP	Deep orange Flakes Pyridine	308(d) 97%	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrFN ₄ O ₂	N=15.51	N=15.82
7.	5-Chloro I + FOP	2-(or 3-)Fluoro-9-Chloro IP	Brownish yellow Granular Pyridine	312(d) 63%	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClFN ₃	N=15.46	N=16.12
8.	3-Bromo AQ + FOP	2-Fluoro-8 (or 9)-bromo AP	Buff coloured cryst. Pyridine	256-57 67%	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrFN ₃	N=7.97	N=8.14
9.	3 : 4-Dinitro AQ + FOP	2-Fluoro-8 : 9-dinitro AP	Buff coloured cryst. Pyridine	270-71 44%	C ₁₄ H ₇ FN ₄ O ₂	N=15.46	N=16.23
10.	3-Chloro AQ + FOP	2-Fluoro-8 (or 9)-Chloro AP	Buff coloured cryst Pyridine	260(d) 68%	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClFN ₃	N=9.13	N=9.24
11.	PQ + FOP	2-Fluoro PP	Light brownish yellow Pyridine	213-14 84%	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ FN ₂	N=9.39	N=9.63
12.	2-Nitro PQ + FOP	2-Fluoro-12-nitro PP	Light yellowish green Pyridine	261-62 43%	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ FN ₂ O ₂	N=12.24	N=13.36
13.	2 : 7-Dinitro PQ + FOP	2-Fluoro-7 : 12-dinitro PP	Light brown Pyridine	285-86 100%	C ₂₀ H ₉ FN ₄ O ₄	N=14.43	N=14.86

Isatin = I, Acenaphthenequinone = AQ, Phenanthraquinone = PQ, 4-Fluoro-*o*-Phenylenediamine = FOP, Indophenazine = IP ; Acenaphthaphenazine = AP ; Phenanthraphenazine = PP.

refluxed for 15 to 20 mins. In a few cases, concentration of the solution to a small volume was necessary. The crystals were filtered, washed with cold acetic acid and recrystallised several times to give the pure products.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of the Bhagalpur University for facilities and one of them (K. K.) is grateful to the U. G. C. for the grant of a teacher fellowship.

References

- N. P. BUU-HOI, R. ROYER, B. ERKART and P. JACQUIGNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4867
- V. Q. YEN, N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1858.
- N. P. BUU-HOI and P. JACQUIGNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3095.
- N. P. BUU-HOI, G. SAINT-RUF, P. JACQUIGNON and M. MARTY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2274.
- N. P. BUU-HOI and G. SAINT-RUF, *Bull.-Soc. Chim., France*, 1960, 1920 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 882.
- J. S. FRIEDMAN, U. S. PATENT 2627, 461, 1953 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 842.
- K. N. SAREEN, R. P. KOHLI, M. K. P. AMMA and M. L. GUZRAL, *Indian J. Physiol Pharmacol*, 1962, 6, 87.
- E. SCHUNEK and L. MARCHLEWSKI, *Ber.*, 1956, 29, 194.
- S. K. GUHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 13, 571.
- H. D. TIWARI and S. D. DUTTA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, (Allahabad) 1937, 71, 58.
- D. PRASAD, S. SEN and P. C. DUTTA, *Ber.*, 1937, 70(II), 2363.
- S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 264.
- S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 815.
- D. PRASAD and P. C. DUTTA, *Ber.*, 1937, 70B, 2365.
- GEORGES RUDALI, HUGUELET CHALEVET and FRANCIS WINTERNITZ, *Compt. rend.*, 1955, 240, 1738.
- A. C. SIRCAR and S. K. GUHA, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1924, 125, 385.
- S. K. GUHA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 582.
- S. K. GUHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423.
- S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 1011.
- A. SVEINEJORNSSON and C. A. VANDER WERF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 869.
- F. C. SCHMELKS and M. RUBIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1631.
- H. K. MITCHELL and C. NIEMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 67, 1232 ; E. L. BANNET and C. NIEMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1800.
- R. DUSCHINSKY and E. PLEVEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4559.
- W. T. SMITH (JR.) and E. C. STRINLE (JR.) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1292.